

INTERNATIONAL COMMERCIAL ARBITRATION AGREEMENT - ISSUE OF AUTONOMY IN ARBITRATION PRACTICE

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Abstract: *The principle of autonomy in international commercial arbitration agreements plays a pivotal role in ensuring the independence and efficiency of arbitration practices. This study explores the concept of autonomy, focusing on its implications for the validity, enforceability, and interpretation of arbitration agreements. Key issues such as the doctrine of separability, party autonomy, and the limits imposed by national laws and public policy are critically analyzed. By examining case law and international conventions, the paper highlights the challenges and opportunities in maintaining autonomy while balancing the interests of justice and fairness. The findings contribute to the ongoing discourse on strengthening arbitration as a preferred mechanism*

Keywords: *International Commercial Arbitration, Arbitration Agreement, Autonomy, Party Autonomy, Doctrine of Separability, Public Policy, Arbitration Practice, Dispute Resolution, and International Law or resolving international commercial disputes.*

Introduction

For parties to submit their future or present disputes to arbitrator there must be an existing arbitration agreement between the parties to do so. It is the arbitration or submission agreement of the parties that form the basis for their reference to an arbitral tribunal. Arbitration agreement is the foundation stone of international commercial arbitration. Arbitration agreement does not only serve as an evidence of the consent of the parties to arbitration and to establish the obligation to arbitrate. It is the basis of the jurisdiction being exercised by the arbitral tribunal. The arbitral tribunal can only exercise such power as the parties may have conferred on it expressly or by necessary implication in the term of their agreement.

The importance of arbitration agreement in international commercial arbitration practice can be understood by reference to the function it performs. Thus the arbitration agreement helps in the following ways-

1. Answering whether or not there should be arbitration at all.
2. Determining the jurisdiction and power of arbitral tribunal.
3. Determining what disputes can be brought before the arbitral tribunal.

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4. Ascertaining to a large extent, the enforceability or otherwise of the ensure arbitral award.
5. The applicable law to dispute and whether the arbitration is *ad hoc* or institutional.
6. It also determines the forum and venue for the arbitration.¹

The agreement to arbitrate may form a clause in the main contract document of the parties. Where it is contained in the main contract document; it is taken to have its own autonomous existence independent of the main contract. It may also be in a separate document independent of the main contract document. The international commercial arbitration agreement must be in writing, but unfortunately, in most jurisdictions, the form of the written nature of the agreement is not expressly provided. *Article II (2) of the New York convention provides that,*

*The term agreement in writing shall include an arbitration clause in a contract or an arbitration agreement signed by the parties or contained in an exchange of letters or telegrams.*²

Also, the UNCIRAL Model Law in its Article 7 (2) provides that –

*The arbitration agreement shall be in writing: An agreement is in writing if it is contained in a document signed by the parties or in an exchange of letter, telex, telegrams or other means of communication which provide a record of the agreement, or in an exchange of statements of claim and defence in which the existence of an agreement is alleged by one part and not denied by another. The reference in a document containing an arbitration clause constitutes an arbitration agreement provided that the contract is in writing and the reference is such as to make that clause part of the contract.*³

It is very important for parties going into international commercial arbitration agreement to ensure that the agreement meets up with the essential elements and requirements of the laws. This is because the making of a valid international arbitration agreement is vital in international arbitration process for without it the entire arbitral tribunal effort and award would be mere nullity, and come to naught. It is in recognition of this singular fact that the New York Convention and the Model Law both emphasized the necessity for a valid arbitration agreement as a precursor to a valid arbitration and an enforceable award. The New York convention states that- the recognition and enforcement of an award may be refused if the arbitration agreement is not valid under the law to which the parties have subject it or, failing any indication thereon, under the law of the country where the award was made.⁴

¹ Prof. Oluwole Akanle, "The Arbitration Agreement", International Commercial Arbitration Workshop Paper of Centre for African Law & Development Studies, 15th September, 1995,iv.

² Redfern & Hunter, *Law & Practice of International Commercial Arbitration*, 1991, 75. See also section 1(1)(a)(b)(c)(2) Arbitration and Conciliation Act CAP A18 LFN 2004. Section 2(1)(2)(3)(4)(5) of the Arbitration and Mediation Act of Nigeria 2023.

³ Article 7(2)of UNCITRAL Model Law.

⁴ Article V(1)(a) of the New York Convention.

*Also the Model Law in its Article 34(2)(a)(i) provides that an award made pursuant to it can be set aside on the application of a party to the court if he furnishes proofs that –
...The said agreement is not valid under the law to which the parties have subjected it or, failing any indication thereon, under the law of this state...⁵*

This implies that the making of valid arbitration agreement is fundamental and paramount in arbitration practice.

Meaning of International Commercial Arbitration

As the two terms “international” and “commercial” are important in this discussion, effort should be made to identify their meanings for proper understanding of the issues involved. The relevant question is, what is meant by international commercial arbitration and how does it differ from domestic arbitration? Whereas national law regulates domestic arbitration, international commercial arbitration is regulated and governed by a variety of law, namely; comparative law, international conventions, and usage of international trade.

Some academics claimed that the international commercial arbitration is governed by the new *lex mercatoria* which is defined as a set of general principles and customary rules elaborated in the framework of international trade without reference to a particular national system of law.⁶ This theory is unacceptable as it is unimaginable that international commercial arbitration is now wholly distinct from national arbitration laws or that it would be practicable to sever all links with such laws. Secondly, so long as the *lex mercatoria* lacks the sanctions of national or international law, it is presumptuous to say that the international commercial arbitration is governed by it. Such a point of view would be unsustainable in legal theory.⁷

International commercial arbitration can at best be defined by defining the two key terms (words) therein, that is, “international” and “commercial”. However there is no agreement among scholars as to what these two terms mean. Nevertheless, an attempt must be made. According to Redfern and Martin Hunter, the term international in this regard is used to mark the difference between arbitration, which are purely national or domestic, and those, which in some way transcend national boundaries, and so are international.⁸

Different marks have been adopted in determining whether arbitration is international or domestic. Some have used two main criteria, either alone or in conjunction in defining the term international, in the context of an international commercial arbitration. In Article 1492 of the French Code, the nature of the dispute is used in analyzing whether a dispute is international and in that context arbitrational

⁵ Article 34(d)(2)(a)(i) of the Model Law. See also Article 36(a)(i) of the Model Law.

⁶ Ola Lando, “The Lex Mercatoria in International Arbitration”, *Comparative Law Quarterly*, Vol.34, 1985, 747.

⁷ Dr. Husain M. Al-Baharna, “International Commercial Arbitration in a Changing World”, *Arab Law Quarterly*, (1993), 144 at 145.

⁸ Redfern & Martin Hunter, *Law and Practice of International Commercial Arbitration*, 7th Ed. 2004, 14.

is international if it involves the interest of international trade.⁹ ICC Rules in 1923 adopted the nature of dispute, as its criterion for deciding whether or not arbitration was an international one under its rules. In 1927, it altered its rules to cover dispute, which contain a foreign element, even if the parties were national of the same country.¹⁰

The European Convention of 1961 in its article 1 (1) (a) defined international arbitration agreement to mean arbitration concluded for the purpose of settling dispute arising from international trade between physical or legal person having, when concluding the agreement, their habitual place of residence or their seat in different contracting state. The Belgium and Switzerland legations used the residence and national of the parties as the test of whether a particular arbitration is international or not.¹¹ The Model Law in its Article 1(3) provides that –

An arbitration is international if;

- (a) *The parties to an arbitration have , at the times of the conclusion that agreement their place of business in different states; or*
- (b) *One of the following place is situated outside the state in which the parties have their place of business;*
 - (i) *The place of arbitration if determined or pursuant, to the arbitration agreement.*
 - (ii) *Any place where a substantial part obligations of the commercial relationship is to be performed which the subject matter of the dispute is most closely connected ; or*
- (c) *The parties have expressly agreed that the parties agreed that the subject matter of the arbitration agreement relates to more than one country*

From this definition, the international character or nature of the arbitration agreement is related to the parties having their place of business in the different States, the subject matter of the dispute itself having close connection with a place foreign to the parties and the place of the arbitration being foreign “situs”

Section 57 (2) of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act 2004 as also in section 91(5) of the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023 of Nigeria states that arbitration is international if

- (a) *The parties to an arbitration agreement have, at the time of the conclusion of their agreement, their places of business in difference countries :or*
 - (b) *One of the following places is situated outside the country in which the parties have their place of business,*
 - (i) *The place of arbitration if such place is determined in or pursuant to the arbitration agreement*
- ;

⁹ Article 1492 of the French Code of Civil Procedure, Decree Law No. 80-500 of 12th May 1981.

¹⁰ Article 1(1) of ICC Rules.

¹¹ Cap 12 Article 176 Swiss Act on Private International Law 18th December, 1987.

(ii) *any place where a substantial part of the obligation of the commercial relationship is to be performed or the place with which subject matter of the dispute is most closely connected;*

(c) *the parties have expressly agreed that the subject matter of the arbitration agreement relates to more than one country; or*

(d) *The place despite the nature of the contract; expressly agreed that any dispute arising from the commercial transaction shall be treated as an international arbitration.*¹²

A careful perusal of both the Model Law and the provisions of section 57 (2) of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act (now section 91(5)(6)(7) of the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023 of Nigeria) will lead to the reasonable conclusion that the only deference between them is the inclusion of section 57 (2) (d) in the Nigeria Act. The definition as put forward in section 57 (2) of the Act 2004 now section 91(5) of the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023 combined the two criteria earlier mentioned, that is, the parties and their nationality or seat of management if it is a corporate entity or a corporation or government, the international nature of the dispute, that is, if the place with which the subject matter is connected is foreign to the parties; if the choice of the place of the arbitration is foreign and finally if the parties have expressly agreed in their contract that any dispute arising from their transaction shall be treated as an international arbitration regardless of the nature of the dispute.

The next issue is the definition of the term (word) “commercial,”. In England the commercial court was established as part of the Queen's Bench Division of the High court in 1970 to deal with commercial action and by order 72 Rule one of the R.S.C. commercial action means---

any cause arising out of the ordinary transaction of merchants and traders and without prejudice to the generality of the foregoing words, any cause relating to the construction of a mercantile document, the export or import of merchandise, affraightment, insurance, banking , mercantile agency and mercantile usage.

The definition as put foreword above is so wide as to encompass all forms of contracts among merchants, traders, and businessmen including those in construction industries. This is also in line with the comment which was advanced by the drafts men of the Model Law when they stated at the foot note of the same that

the term commercial should be given a wide interpretation so as to cover matter arising from all relationship of a commercial nature, whether contractual or not. Relationships of a commercial nature include, but are not limited to the following transactions: any trade transaction for the supply or exchange of goods or services, distribution agreement: factoring leasing; Construction works; consulting, engineering licensing; investment; financing; banking; insurance; exploitation

¹² Section 91(5) Arbitration and Mediation Act of Nigeria 2023.

*agreement or concession; joint venture and other forms of industrial or business co-operation; carriage of goods or passenger by air, sea, rail or road.*¹³

Section 57 (1) of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act 2004 (now section 91(1) of the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023) defined the term commercial in the very language of the Model Law. The aforesaid section states that—

Commercial means all relationship of a commercial nature including any trader transaction for the supply or exchange of goods or services distribution agreement, commercial representation or agency, factoring, leasing investment financing, banking, insurance, exploitation agreement or concession, joint venture and other forms of industrial or business co-operation, carriage of goods or passenger by air, sea, rail or by road.

The definition in section 57 (1) of the Act 2004 now section 91(1) of 2023 Act largely reproduced the text in one of the footnotes to Model Law mentioning a number of different transactions that would qualify as commercial. As stated by an erudite scholar, Dr Amazu A. Asouzu, section 57 (1) of the Act now section 91 (1) of 2023 Act appears to have added to the body of law, a greater degree of certainty as the meaning of “commercial” although the list of commercial transactions given in the Act, like the list in the foot note to the Model Law is a –exhaustive one.¹⁴ The essence of defining the term commercial is to distinguish between contracts, which are commercial, and those, which are not because in some jurisdiction only contractual contracts can be subject of arbitration agreement. This explains why time and space were devoted in the definition of commercial and international in this work.

Enforcement of International Commercial Arbitration Agreement

Parties to international commercial arbitration agreement have a duty to abide by the terms of their agreement. A party should not be allowed to withdraw from the same or abandon his agreement and resort to litigation. It is the duty of the court when requested, to ensure that parties keep to the terms of their agreement.

If an agreement to arbitration cannot be recognize and enforced by the court when there is non-compliance with it by a party who instituted a competing or parallel suit in relation to the matter agreed to be referred, arbitration will degenerate into ordinary court room litigation and will as a result lose much of its practical attraction and efficacy.¹⁵ Generally, these are two principal ways of enforcing

¹³ This passage appeared as the foot note to Article 1. 1 of the Model Law which states that it applies to international commercial arbitration.

¹⁴ Amazu A. Asouzu, “The Legal Framework for Commercial Arbitration and Conciliation in Nigeria” *ICSID Review- Foreign Investment Law Journal*, 1995, 214 at 215.

¹⁵ Amasu A. Asouzu, “The Egyptian Law Concerning Arbitration in Civil and Commercial Matters,” *The African Journal of International and Comparative Law*, 1996, 139 at 147.

international commercial arbitration agreement. The first is by stay of proceeding and the second is by section at law for breach of contract, the remedy of which is found on damages.

In Article 11 (3) of the New York Convention and sections 4 and 5 of Arbitration and Conciliation Act 2004 now section 5 of the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023 of Nigeria, stay of proceeding by the national court is provided for. Article 11 (3) of the New York Convention provide that -

The court of a contracting state, when seised of an action in a matter in respect of which the party have made an agreement within the meaning of this article shall at the request of one of the parties, refer the parties to arbitration, unless it finds said agreement is null and void in operative and incapable of being performed.

Article 8 (1) of the UNCITRAL Model Law while dealing on the same subject matter added a clause, which is lacking in *Article 11 (3) of New York Convention* by providing that the request must be made before the applicant takes a step in the proceeding. Article 8 (1) of the Model Law provide inter alia- *A court before which an action is brought in a matter which is the subject of an arbitration agreement shall, if a party so request not later than when submitting his first statement on the substance of the dispute, refer the parties to arbitration unless it finds that the agreement is null and void, inoperative or incapables of being performed.*¹⁶

The meaning of this is that the application must be made by a party to the agreement and it must be made before taking any step in the proceeding as the applicant shall be deemed to have waived his right if the application or request is made after taking a step in the proceedings. The application shall be made to the court and not to an arbitral tribunal. As to what constitutes taking a step in the proceeding, the Supreme Court of Nigeria had in *Kano State Urban Development Board Vs. Fanz Construction Co. Ltd*¹⁷ gave a detailed list of the same.

Another method of enforcing international commercial arbitration agreement is by action at law but this is a common law method which is not provided for in the Arbitration and Mediation Act. For the court to enforce agreement by award of damage to the aggrieved party, it must be shown that the arbitration agreement is not null and void, inoperative or incapable of being performed.¹⁸ It had been suggested though informally that order of specific preference could be made so as to enforce the arbitration agreement. My reaction to this view is that arbitration agreement is a simple agreement and that order of specific performance cannot issue to enforce it.

Impeachment of International Commercial Arbitration Agreement

There are a number of ways and ground pursuant to which an arbitration agreement could be challenged or attacked. The grounds for impeachment are dependent on the law involved and the

¹⁶ Article 8(1) of the UNCITRAL Model Law.

¹⁷ *K.S.U.D.B. V. Fanz Construction Co. Ltd* (1990)NWLR (Pt.142)1

¹⁸ Article 11(3)New York Convention. Article 8(1) o f the UNCITRAL Model Law. *Dalmia Dairy Industries Ltd. V. National Bank of Pakistan* (1978)2 Lloyd's Rep. 223.

procedure for challenge also depends on the stage of arbitration proceedings at which the challenge or attack is raised. The court will either refuse to hear a challenge to the arbitration agreement or will only permit it to prevail if it is obviously justified. The challenge could be made either to the court or the arbitral tribunal depending on the ground for the challenge and the stage of the arbitral proceedings at which the attack was raised.

In America, Sweden, and Germany, an application challenging the agreement of the parties particularly on the issue of jurisdiction can be made to court at any time. In Switzerland, no such application can be made to the court unless it had first been made before the arbitrators and they expressed their opinions on the same. Again, under the English, US, German, and Swedish law, a party resisting arbitration will succeed if he proves that the arbitration agreement is unenforceable.¹⁹ In Nigeria, a party to the arbitration agreement can apply to the arbitral tribunal challenging its jurisdiction and this can be done at any stage before the arbitral tribunal marks its final award.²⁰ Where the arbitral tribunal had rendered its final award before attack on its jurisdiction is raised, the application shall be made to the court for the impeachment of the arbitration agreement and the award respectively.

There are several ground pursuant to which an arbitration agreement could be impeached. These grounds are –

1. **Formal Validity of The Arbitration Agreement;** one of the requirement for an international commercial arbitration agreement is that it must be valid under the law to which the party have subjected it or failing any indication thereon, under the law of the country where the award was made.²¹ Fortunately, this constitutes one of the grounds for impeaching an arbitration award pursuant to article v (a) of New York Convention. Article v(1) (a) of the New York Convention provides that, “*the recognition and enforcement of an award may be refused if the arbitration agreement itself is not valid.*”

2. **Arbitrability of the Subject Matter:-** not all subject matters are arbitrable. Only issue which can be settled by accord and satisfaction could be subject matters of arbitration. Criminal matters are not arbitrable as they are issues which can only be determined by court of competent jurisdiction for public good. Dissolution of marriage (divorce) under the Act is not arbitrable as the Matrimonial Causes Act provides that it is only the State High Court that has jurisdiction to deal with such matter.

3. **Capacity of the Contracting Parties:-** The capacity to make an arbitration agreement is coextensive with capacity to contract. Any person capable of entering into a contract may be a party to an arbitration agreement.²² The applicable rules governing incapacity of a person to enter into

¹⁹ *M. S. T. Corporation Ltd v. Kate Shipping Ltd.* (1988)WLR 767. M.Mustill & Boyd, *The Law and Practice f Commercial Arbitration in England*, 2nd Ed. Butterworth, London, 1989, 525.

²⁰ Section 12 Arbitration and Conciliation Act Cap A18 L.F.N. 2004. See also section 14(1) Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023.

²¹ Redfern and Martin Hunter, *Law and Practice of International Commercial Arbitration*, 7th Ed, 2004, 148.

²² Article V(1) of the New York Convention.

arbitration agreement are by no means uniform. For natural person, capacity may depend on his nationality or his place of usual residence whereas for corporations capacity may depend on the law of the place of incorporation, the place of business, and the memo and article of incorporation of the corporate entity.

4. **Fraud, under influence and pervasiveness:-** Arbitration agreement could be impeached on the ground of fraud, undue influence and pervasiveness. If the arbitration agreement was obtained by fraud, on the application of any of the parties thereto, the court shall set aside the agreement as not being a voluntary act of the parties.

Autonomy of International Commercial Arbitration Practice

Having considered the issues in respect of international commercial arbitration agreement, the next issue is to determine whether international commercial arbitration practice found on the basis of the said agreement enjoy legal autonomy as put forward by some scholars. Some scholars had in the past considered and regarded international commercial arbitration to be transnational in the sense of being independent of national law. According to Sir Michael John Mustill for example, international arbitration is deemed to be transnational arbitration. The essence of this is that institution of international commercial arbitration is an autonomous juristic entity which is independent of all national court and all national system of law.²³ The views as expressed by the exponents of this idea seen to be that international commercial arbitration transcends national frontiers, and that, it is a procedural system divorced of all municipal system. For these groups of scholars, arbitration attracted neither the support nor the control of the courts. In fact, they presented an arbitration practice floating on a firmament devoid of any national legal connection.

As a matter of fact, their theory on transnational and delocalization in its purest form means that international commercial arbitration is distinct and autonomous system, permitted to float free of regulation by law of the place where the arbitration is held or any other law, all necessary international procedural norms being generated from within the system itself.

The idea of autonomy in international commercial arbitration is certain but also relative. This is because autonomy as I know it, means that the arbitration agreement is independent of the main contract of transaction between the parties and also that the proceeding shall be in accordance with the agreement of the parties and in the line with the applicable law agreed by the parties or their arbitrators. This does not mean that the court of the place or that the national law of the venue of arbitration proceeding or place of enforcement or impeachment has no role to play in international commercial arbitration practice.

it is highly unacceptable that international commercial arbitration practices should exist in this form of extreme autonomy as the so called “pure theory” presented above states, not that they are subject to a

²³ Sir Michael John Mustill, *International Commercial and Maritime Arbitration*, 1988, 133

different legal regime from the others but that they are subject to no legal regime at all unless as the parties prescribed in their agreement without any relationship to either the legal regime of the place of arbitration, the legal regime of the parties, or the place of enforcement or impeachment. Such a legal proposition as the one above which must be quite unique in any field of legal activity, can be supported only if it is obvious that this is the result, which commercial men desire.²⁴

The problem inherent in this theory of extreme autonomy, and transnationalism will be more apparent and obvious if not turns to the practical aspect as the logical view of transnationalism demands that the parties are taken to have renounced all ties with domestic law, not simply those which the parties find constricting. In such a circumstance if the mechanism for appointing the tribunal breaks down, or if there is a causal vacancy, the court cannot and should not lend its help. If an important party fails or refuses to attend the hearing or if a party fails to honour the award, the successful party shall be helpless or if there exist lacuna in the law agreed by the parties the arbitral panel cannot look into other laws to fill the gap as reasonable men.

This may be an acceptable practices where the people involved in international commercial arbitration practice are members of a closed society or trade in which case moral sanction could have the same effect of legal force. But the field in which this transnational theory operates is so wide that the need for a legal force is required so as to ensure compliance by a recalcitrant party. International commercial arbitration practice cannot exist without an internal procedural law. No businessmen should tolerate a system for resolving disputes which at worst, has no procedural principles at all, and at best has no means of enforcing whatever principles there may be. This idea of extreme and absolute autonomy is unacceptable and does not exist as there cannot be a legal process in float sequence unconnected with the law of the place of arbitration and absolutely in accordance with the agreement of the parties and no more, where even there may exist some form of lacuna or where there is need for compulsion so as to bring the agreement of the parties in conformity with fairness and legality.²⁵

Forms of Arbitration in International Commercial Arbitration Practice

Thought extreme and pure autonomy as presented by Sir Michael John Mustill does not exist, mild autonomy in international commercial arbitration practice exists. Autonomy exists in difference form and it is to these forms of autonomy that emphasis will be focused.

1. Autonomy of arbitration clause;-

In international commercial arbitration practice and arbitration practice generally, the arbitration clause is autonomous and independent of the main contract of transaction between the parties. It does not suffer the same fate with the main contract of transaction between the parties. Article 21 (2) of the UNCITRAL Arbitration Rules provides that, “an arbitration clause which forms part of a contract and

²⁴ Sir Michael John Mustill, *International Commercial and Maritime Arbitration*, 1988, 133.

²⁵ Holtzmann, *Arbitration and the Courts: Partners in a System of International Jurisdiction*”, *Rev de Arbitration*, 1978,253. Henry P. de Vries, “International Commercial Arbitration: A Transnational View” *Journal of International Arbitration*, 1993, 7 at 8.

which provides for arbitration under the rules shall be treated as an agreement independent to the other terms of the contract.”

This implies that arbitration clause is both separable and severable from the main contract between the parties in respect of the substantive transaction. Whereas the main contract concerns itself with the transaction between the parties, arbitration clause concerns itself with the dispute, which has arisen, and no more.²⁶

Arbitration clause in a contract of transaction between the parties comes to the surface and rekindles itself at the occurrence of dispute and wrongful termination of contract. This explains the reasoning of Lord Mac Millian in *Heyman v. Darwins Ltd.*²⁷ wherein he stated thus-

Total breach of contract ... does not abrogate the contract, though it may relieve the injured party of the duty of further fulfilling the obligations, which he has by the contract undertaken to the repudiating party. The contract is not put out of existence, though all further performance of obligation undertaken by each party in favour of the other may cease. It survives for the purpose of measuring the claim arising out of the breach, and the arbitration clause survives for determining the mode of their settlement. The purposes of the contract have failed, but the arbitration clause is not one of the purposes of the contract.

Immediately after executing the main transactional agreement of the parties or executing the arbitration agreement, if it is on a different document, the arbitration clause goes into abeyance and remain so until there is dispute within the four corners of the contract entered into by the parties. However, a decision by the arbitral tribunal that the contract of transaction between the parties is null and void shall not entail "ipso jure" the validity of the arbitration clause.

2. Autonomy of Parties

Arbitration is a private process in the settlement of disputes. As it is a private process, the parties are allowed the freedom and right to determine a wide range of issues in their arbitration agreement. The parties are at liberty to determine the application law to the dispute. Where parties agreed as to the applicable law, all other forms of law play complementary role. The applicable laws in the arbitration practice automatically become the laws agreed by the parties. The laws of the venue of arbitration practice, place of enforcement and impeachment will apply where there is lacuna.

It is for the parties to agree as to the form of arbitration suitable for their purpose (whether institutional arbitration or ad hoc) and whether a sole arbitrator shall be appointed. The parties have the right to even name the arbitrator or prescribe an office holder as their arbitrator. The Act will only come in when the parties failed to agree among themselves as to the number of arbitrators or where the agreement of the parties is silent on the issue. This explains the reasoning in *Section 6 of the Act. Section*

²⁶ *Prima Paint Corporation v. Conklin Manufacturing Co.* 18 L. Ed 2nd 1276. See section 12 (2) Arbitration and Conciliation Act Cap A18 L.F.N. 2004. See also section 14(2) Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023.

²⁷ (1942)AC 356 at 374.

6 of the Act provides that, *"the parties to an arbitration agreement may determine the number of arbitration to be appointed under agreement, but where no such determination is made, the number of arbitration shall deemed to be three."* The new Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023 in its section 6 (1) (2) provides that, "the parties to an arbitration agreement may agree on the number of arbitrators to constitute an arbitral tribunal. Where there is no agreement at to the number of arbitrators, the arbitral tribunal shall consist of a sole arbitrator."²⁸

This means that the parties to the arbitration agreement have the autonomy of determining the numbers of arbitrators. The Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023 will only come in where parties failed to reach any agreement on this matter.

The autonomy of parties in arbitration extends to the issues in respect of the applicable law, applicable procedure, and the venue of arbitration proceedings. All these issue are vital for the proper conduct of arbitration proceeding. The right to determine the applicable law, arbitral procedure, and venue of arbitration, is one reserved for the parties. For example, Section 35 (1) Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023 provides that, the parties are free to agree on the language or languages to be used in the arbitral proceedings and where there is no agreement, the language to be used is English." The provisions of section 18(2) of the former Arbitration and Conciliation Act 2004 on this matter are more satisfactory and flexible. It provides that, "the parties may by agreement determine the language or languages to be used in the arbitral proceedings, but where they do not do so the arbitral tribunal shall determine the languages to be used bearing in mind the relevant circumstance of the case." To insist that the applicable language in the absence of the agreement of the parties shall be English without considering the parties, their witnesses and the possible venue of arbitration may work hardship on the parties and the arbitral tribunal.

The simple implication of the provisions of sections 35(1) of Arbitration and Mediation Act and 18(2) of Arbitration and Conciliation Act above is that the parties have the right to determine the applicable language to be used in arbitral proceedings and any language agreed upon by the parties shall unless a contrary intention is expressed by the parties, be the language or languages to be used in any written statements by the parties, in any hearing, award, decision or any other communication in the course of the arbitration.²⁹

Where the parties in their agreement determine the applicable law to the dispute the arbitral tribunal shall apply the agreed law to the exclusion of all other law unless where there is lacuna. This view has the support of section 47 (10) of the Act which provides that *"the arbitral tribunal shall decide the dispute in accordance with the rules if force in the country whose laws the parties have chosen as applicable the substance dispute."*

²⁸ Section 6(1) (2) Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023 of Nigeria.

²⁹ Section 35(1) Arbitration and Mediation ACT 2023. See also section 18 (2) Arbitration and Conciliation Act 2004.

The only circumstance in which the tribunal may determine the applicable law is where the parties failed to prescribe same in their agreement. However, the tribunal has the discretion, to consider and take account of the usage of the trade applicable to the transaction while making its final award on the dispute. This explain why the Act in its *Section 47 (5)* prescribed that, “in all casa, the arbitral tribunal shall decried in accordance with the terms of the contract and shall take account of the usage of the trade applicable to the transaction”³⁰

The arbitral tribunal shall not decide *ex aequo et bono* or as *amiable compositeur* unless the parties have authorized it to do so.³¹The parties to the agreement may on their own agree as to the applicable procedure in the arbitration. The parties can agree that there will be no oral hearing; that the arbitration is to be on documents only; that there are to be no opening statement or that such statement should be limited to a prescribed length; that all evidence in chief is to be in the form of written statement to be exchange before hearing and that witnesses should only be required to attend when the other side has indicated that they wish to cross – examine. Where the parties agreed in advance that these steps were to be taken, such an agreement would undoubtedly be binding.³²

3. Autonomy of The Arbitrator

The parties have the right to determine issues of venue of arbitration, arbitral procedure, language of arbitration, and the applicable law or the governing law. There are circumstances wherein the parties for reasons of disagreement may decide to be silent on any of these issues and in which case provision of the Act will apply. In such situation, where the agreement of the parties is silent on such issue, the arbitral tribunal shall determine them in its own. The task of determining the applicable law in the absence of the agreement of the parties, rests in the arbitrate tribunal. The same applies to the language to be used in the arbitral proceedings. Section 18 (1) of the Act 2004 provides that, "The parties may by agreement determine the language or languages to be used in the arbitral proceeding, but where they do not do so, the arbitral tribunal shall determine the language or language to be used bearing in mind the relevant circumstance of the case." However, section 35 of the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023 provides that, “the parties are free to agree on the language or languages to be used in the arbitral proceedings and where there is no agreement, the language to be used is English.” This has not derogated from the provisions of the former Act that the arbitrators determine the applicable language or languages in the absence of the agreement by the parties. This is because section 35(2) of the Act further provides that,

Any language or languages agreed upon by the parties or determined by the arbitral tribunal under subsection (1) shall, unless the parties or the arbitral tribunal state otherwise, be the language or

³⁰ Section 15 subsections 1-5 of the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023.

³¹ Section 15(4) of the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023.

³² Prof Micael P. Furmston, "The Autonomy of Arbitrator," *Arbitration*, Vol. 58, No.2 May, 1992, 75. *D.S.T. v. Raknoc* (1987)ALL ER 769. *Home & Overseas Insurance v. Mentor Insurance* (1989)3All ER 74.

languages to be used in any written statements by the parties, in any hearing, award decision or any other communication in the course of the arbitration.

On the issue of place of arbitration, unless the parties agreed to the contrary the arbitral tribunal shall determine the venue of the arbitration. Section 32(1) (2) of the Arbitration and Mediation Act provides that,

(1) The seat of the arbitration shall be designated-

(a) By the parties to the arbitration agreement;

(b) By an arbitral tribunal or other institution or person authorized by the parties with power in that regard; or

(c) Subject to subsection (2), by the arbitral tribunal.

(2) Where the parties have not designated the seat of the arbitration and they have not authorized any arbitral or other institution to designate the seat of the arbitration, the seat of the arbitration shall be any place in Nigeria as the arbitral tribunal may determine, unless the arbitral tribunal decides that a place in a place in another country should be the seat of the arbitration having regard to all the relevant circumstances, including ...

Mention must be made that even when parties agreed as to the place of arbitration, the arbitral tribunal has right to change the same unless the venue is made exclusive by the parties. The arbitral tribunal taking into consideration the circumstance of the venue to the parties and their witnesses, may decide to change the venue so as not to work hardship against the parties involved.

4 Forum Autonomy

The parties have the autonomy to determine the forum of arbitration and where it fails the parties, the arbitral tribunal shall determine same taking into consideration the circumstances of the arbitration and the parties including their witnesses and the world view of the state or country in question. If the parties had agreed as to a particular forum or territory as the place of arbitration, any proceedings in any other forum or place shall be deemed to have been made without jurisdiction particularly where the forum is made exclusive by the parties. For the arbitral tribunal to change the forum as agreed by the parties, the consent of parties is required.³³

Where however the forum is made exclusive, the arbitrators may change same without their final award being affected in any way particularly where the circumstances of the change is reasonable and fair to both parties to the agreement. In changing the arbitration forum or venue the arbitral tribunal shall

³³ *Spilade Maritime Corporation v. Cansulex Ltd.* (1986)3All ER 843. *Bank of Tokyo Ltd. V. Karoom.* (1987)AC 45. *Trendtex Trading Corporation v. Credit Suisse* (1980)3All ER 721. *Muduroglo v. T.C. Ziraat Bankasi* (1986)QB 1225. *Evans Marshall Co. Ltd. V. Bertola* (1973)1WLR 349 at 361. *European Asian Bank AG v. Punjab & Sind Bank* (1982)Lloyd's Rep. 356. *Dimskel Shipping Co. S.A. v. International Transport Workers Federation, The Evia Luck* (1986)2Lloy's Rep. 165. In all these cases the idea is that the consent of the parties must be obtained before change of the arbitration venue agreed by the parties. The agreement of the parties on the issue of venue may be made exclusive and in which case the place may be an exclusive venue which may be difficult to change by any person. It is for the party pleading an exclusive venue to prove same.

take into cognizance the existence of a more appropriate forum, convenience and expenses on the parties, availability of the witnesses to the forum, the law governing the relevant transaction, the place where the parties reside or carry on business, and the world view of the court in the area, whether their world view is parochial or international in character and nature. However, whether the venue is made exclusive or not, the consent of the parties shall be obtained before any change of same by the arbitral tribunal. The parties must be given notices of the circumstance and reasons necessitating such change of venue. The reason for this is obvious, parties agree as to venue for reasons of convenience and neutrality. The arbitral tribunal must ensure that none of the parties gains unfair advantage over the other because of the change of the venue.

Conclusion

For parties to embark on arbitration there must be an agreement between them to do so. International commercial arbitration agreement must be in writing. Its written nature may take different forms. The agreement may be a clause in the contract of transaction between the parties. It may also be in a separate document signed by both parties. From the discussion so far, it is obvious that there is autonomy in arbitration practice but not the type of autonomy as presented by Sir Michael John Mustill. What we have is a mild form of autonomy and not a pure form of autonomy. It is difficult to have arbitration practice which can be absolutely independent of the law of the place of arbitration and unconnected with the legal system of the place of enforcement or impeachment of an arbitral award. Arbitration practice cannot be absolutely independent of the court. This is because arbitration needs the court for a lot of things. Without an efficient court system, arbitration practice will die a natural death. This is because arbitration has no machinery or mechanism for enforcement or impeachment of its award without the assistance of the court. Arbitration has no means of compelling the witness or appointing arbitrators to fill a casual vacancy without the aid of the court.